

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF BREADWINNERS AS A RESULT OF JOB LOSS DURING THE PANDEMIC

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue10

Pages: 1109-1127

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2126

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13181562

Manuscript Accepted: 06-22-2024

Lived Experiences of Breadwinners as a Result of Job Loss During the Pandemic

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic struck the world and rapidly caused economic and health damage among people, and because of the economic impact caused by this pandemic, it has now become one of the major concerns in terms of psychological health, most especially of family breadwinners who lost their jobs. The Phenomenological Qualitative Research Design was employed in this study. It aimed to characterize primary breadwinners' experiences, such as their experience of abruptly losing their work during the epidemic. Internal psychological processes, such as their personal experiences and connections with others, were also considered. This study was conducted with ten (10) breadwinners who lost their jobs and are currently living in N.C.R. This study employed a purposive sampling technique. The participants underwent a validation as part of the selection of respondents for the study, participants that met the study criteria proceeded to the interview process. Seven (7) criteria had to be firmly met: (1) Breadwinners, people who brought in the main source of income of the family who lost their jobs due to redundancy or downsizing, (2) can either be male or female (3) ages from 20 years old to 45 years old, (4) must be married (5) must have at least have 5 years and above work experience in any field such as corporate and fieldwork, (7) can either be a high school or college graduate. In selecting the participants, the researchers considered only those who could respond to the interview. Also, the participants were asked to answer a qualifier question and then a list of semi-structured questions. The findings show two major themes (1) Positive Realizations and (2) Negative outcomes. In conclusion, for the breadwinners, the process of strengthening the bond between family members and establishing a good support system is essential to have a strong relationship with the members of the family as well as to be able to cope with the stress brought by the pandemic situation. The recommendations based on the findings are strong family bonds, quality time, a support system, self-enhancement, stress management, coping mechanisms, and good communication between the breadwinners and their families.

Keywords: *breadwinners, job loss, pandemic*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has shocked and caused panic as it quickly spread almost around the world, prompting the World Health Organization to declare a global pandemic back in early 2020. Without any authorized vaccine when it started, governments were compelled to use quarantine and social distance to decrease the spread of the virus, flatten the disease's development curve, and lessen the risk of health-care system collapse. The pandemic, alongside the necessary metrics to aid in its management and control, caused significant psychological, social, and economic consequences. From a psychological standpoint, it has caused a wide range of mental difficulties, including anxiety and sadness, as well as varied degrees of stress disorders (Wang, 2020).

Vieira (2021) states that from an economic perspective, there is a clear impact on higher unemployment and financial difficulty for many firms, particularly micro and small businesses and families. Unemployment, particularly in Metro Manila, spiked owing to the impact of the pandemic on the country's economy, according to the Philippine Statistics Authority in 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic not only had a great effect on public health but also affected the economy badly, forcing companies to shut down, resulting in a sudden loss of jobs for some individuals (Fornano, 2020). From a psychological perspective, the resulting unemployment has been found to have an impact on the individual's mental health.

The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was most felt by the breadwinners or the providers of the family. Breadwinners have dependents who rely on them for financial assistance (Zuo, 2004). Being the one providing for his family's financial needs places significant weight and pressure on a breadwinner; thus, finding himself in a state of being unemployed during the pandemic can greatly affect his mental state.

Due to the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is safe to say that changes in the environment demand adaptation; stress is often sensed when the demands of a situation overwhelm one's capacity to cope successfully with those expectations (Lazarus, 1984). The threat, danger, or possible harm (e.g., risk of serious illness or death from the coronavirus), loss (e.g., of loved ones, income, status, employment), uncertainty and unpredictability (e.g., changing health guidance, insecure access to childcare, introduction of new variants), and lack of control are especially likely to be perceived as stressful and are powerful predictors of the emergence of mental health problems (Brown, 1995). In this study, the researchers sought to understand how breadwinners who lost their employment coped, recovered, and moved on, as well as the factors that helped them. The research seeks to understand breadwinners who lost their employment during the COVID-19 epidemic and their experiences. The focus is on their life progression, what helped and encouraged them to change, and what they learned from their experiences.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to investigate the lived experiences of breadwinners who lost their jobs as a result of the pandemic. The researchers was guided by the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of breadwinners who had lost their jobs during the pandemic?
2. How did the breadwinners who were the primary earners for their families and lost their employment during the epidemic navigate their own experiences within the overarching themes?
3. What insights can be gleaned from these experiences?

Literature Review

Pessimism of breadwinners

According to Rodman (2022), the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in significant societal changes that need ongoing adjustment. Not unexpectedly, there has been an increase in stress-related mental disorders in both children and adults throughout the pandemic. The researchers analyze these tendencies by using several key conceptual frameworks that explore the connection between stress and psychopathology. Some of these models focus on characteristics of environmental stressors, such as the accumulation of risks, particular types of stressors, and approaches that increase sensitivity to stress. Identifying the specific components of environmental pressures that are most likely to lead to psychopathology might aid in determining individuals who may need psychiatric treatment. The researchers analyze data supporting each stress model within the framework of past extensive disruptions at the community level, such as natural calamities and acts of terrorism, while also considering emerging evidence from the COVID-19 pandemic. The text discusses the therapeutic implications of developing treatments to reduce mental disorders caused by stress during the pandemic. It emphasizes the use of fast and digital interventions, which may be more accessible than conventional professional services.

Arslan (2020) sought to examine how optimism-pessimism and psychological inflexibility influence the relationship between stress caused by the coronavirus and psychological problems in adults. The study's sample size consisted of 451 people, with women accounting for 55 percent of the total. Most participants were young persons aged 18 to 65, with an average age of 23.30 years. The mediation model revealed that the stress caused by the Coronavirus had a significant predictive impact on optimism-pessimism, psychological inflexibility, and psychological illnesses. Moreover, the impact of stress caused by the coronavirus on psychological challenges in adults was influenced by their levels of optimism-pessimism and psychological inflexibility. Ultimately, the relationship between optimism and pessimism was shown to be a predictor of psychiatric problems in adults, namely via the mechanism of psychological inflexibility.

In his study, Rivot (2019) examined the distinct contrast that Keynes established in the General Theory between voluntary unemployment and involuntary unemployment. In Keynesian economics, voluntary unemployment encompasses a broad range of factors such as wage negotiating defects and inadequate credentials. In order to accurately comprehend involuntary unemployment, the researcher disregarded the matter of a specific decrease in nominal salary at a local level. The focus is on the impact of a widespread decline in money-wages on the overall long-term expectations. Notably, Keynes stops using this language after the General Theory and instead discusses the difference between structural unemployment and demand-deficiency unemployment.

Parents' lost employment and its effects on children and family

In Mooi-Reci's (2019) study, the researchers examined how parents' unemployment affected their children's scholastic achievement in the future. The research's theoretical value lies in its examination of the mediating role of changing work ethics among parents throughout times of unemployment. The research results were derived from a cohort of 812 Dutch children who experienced their parents' joblessness during the preceding economic downturn in the early 1980s. The data was collected from several surveys and administrative sources. The results indicate a clear inverse correlation between the duration of fathers' unemployment and the academic performance of their children. Additionally, there is an indirect correlation mediated by the changing views of mothers towards employment. The researchers also found concrete evidence that as parents' views towards work become more pessimistic, their children's academic performance declines.

According to Stephanie Pappas' literature from 2020, when compared to previous studies conducted before the COVID-19 pandemic, people reported higher levels of despair, stress, and anxiety. Specifically, individuals who lost their jobs during the pandemic expressed even higher levels of negative emotional states. Nevertheless, those with significant psychological resilience had lower levels of melancholy, worry, and stress. Moreover, research on moderation indicated that there is a relationship between mindfulness training (MT) and employment position when it comes to predicting levels of depression, anxiety, and stress. The results of our study indicate that MT might potentially mitigate the adverse effects of the pandemic on patients' mental health. However, more longitudinal research is necessary to validate these findings. The research found that unemployment has a causal effect: longitudinal studies show that individuals who are unemployed have gains in their mental health when they get new work. Research on factory closures, in which all employees lose their jobs simultaneously, reveals that almost all individuals who are laid off have subsequent reductions in their mental health. This provides proof that job loss has a detrimental impact on mental well-being, rather than those with pre-existing worse mental health being more prone to unemployment. Individuals experience more severe hardships as the duration of their unemployment

extends, with those unemployed for a period of six months or longer exhibiting the most unfavorable outcomes in terms of mental well-being.

According to Parolin (2020), the COVID-19 epidemic has led to substantial levels of unemployment in developed countries. Nevertheless, the financial burdens of unemployment have not been distributed evenly across all families. Households with dependent children and parents who are jobless have reported notably elevated levels of adversity, which might potentially have enduring implications for the well-being and growth of the children. There is a need to prioritize the examination of the potential consequences of the increase in parental unemployment. Since the beginning of the pandemic, there has been a significant increase in the percentage of children with a parent who is unemployed, meaning they are without a job and actively seeking work. This increase has reached unprecedented levels in the United States. Families should not endure hardship due to a dearth of employment opportunities. Nevertheless, the convergence of unemployment with an inadequate welfare system and restricted support for local professions might promptly result in heightened levels of distress.

According to Wang's (2021) research, the loss of a parent's job leads to an escalation in conflict between parents and children. This conflict, in turn, is associated with a decrease in the child's good emotions and an increase in negative emotions. Moreover, the fact that parents were working from home (WFH) was associated with an increase in parental warmth. This increase in warmth was shown to be a predictor of higher levels of positive affect in children and lower levels of negative affect in children. Parents from low-income households had a higher probability of job loss and had a lower likelihood of working from home compared to parents from homes with moderate to high income. Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, teenagers from families facing financial hardship and changes in employment faced changes in the way they interacted with their parents, which had an impact on their emotional well-being. Effects of unemployment. It is essential for health physicians to acknowledge these changes in family ecology in order to assess mental health, evaluate current family resources, and provide timely and targeted guidance on stress management and coping with family discord.

Children who have been subjected to family violence, including child abuse, neglect, and intimate partner violence, are more vulnerable to experiencing difficulties during the COVID-19 epidemic. The researchers conducted interviews with IPV advocates, child protective services (CPS) caseworkers, and IPV and CPS administrators to gather information on the specific requirements of children who are exposed to family violence amidst the epidemic. Four topics emerged from this effort. Participants discussed the effects of social isolation, school closures, and distance schooling on children who had been subjected to parental violence. In addition, they discussed child custody and visitation matters, namely when abusive spouses exploit custody arrangements to control survivors of intimate partner violence. They also highlighted limitations on virtual visiting in general. Children hailing from disadvantaged neighborhoods have extra challenges due to structural disparities. This study is an early investigation of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on children who have been subjected to parental abuse (Risser, 2022).

Hong's (2022) research indicates that the majority of folks have more leisure time to spend at home engaging in games with their family during the COVID-19 pandemic. The majority of individuals engage in activities with their family members as a means of maintaining social distance. The present research used a boating game called River Survival, which was played collaboratively using the Switch gaming console, to examine the impact of individuals' familial closeness on their gaming experience and perceived value of participation. This research specifically targeted those who had engaged in the game with their family members. They received notifications via Facebook and Line groups dedicated to certain interests, and they filled out the questionnaire on a website. Family closeness positively influenced the sense of flow, but there was no significant correlation with game anxiety. The occurrence of flow experience was shown to have a positive impact on perceived value, but gaming anxiety did not have a significant impact on perceived value. The study's finding suggests that the absence of closeness among team members prevents players from experiencing a state of flow or seeing the worth of the game.

The pandemic and mental health connection

In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a growing focus on unemployment and its potential adverse consequences. The researchers examined three main aspects: (1) the correlation between unemployment and psychological distress among Israeli individuals aged 20 to 35 during the coronavirus pandemic; (2) the association between various psychological resources and risk factors with psychological distress; and (3) whether these resources and risk factors acted as moderators in the link between unemployment and psychological distress. In April 2020, a survey was performed using snowball sampling to examine the connections between unemployment, psychological resources, risk factors, and psychological distress. The researcher used hierarchical linear models for analysis. There was a correlation between unemployment and increased levels of psychological distress. Amidst the crisis, the presence of trust, optimism, and a feeling of control alleviated psychological distress, while experiencing financial difficulties and isolation exacerbated it. The relationship between unemployment and psychological distress remained unchanged regardless of the number of resources and risk factors in people. Policymakers must design and enhance health initiatives. Designed to address the negative effects on mental health caused by unemployment due to COVID-19 and to support young job seekers in finding employment via labor market initiatives. These endeavors, which are in accordance with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, should be regarded as a crucial method of advancing public health (Netta, 2020).

Increasing apprehension surrounds the welfare of the general populace and their mental state due to the global societal and personal ramifications of the COVID-19 epidemic. The present work contributes to the existing body of COVID-19 research by examining the

influence of mental toughness (MT) on the prediction of negative emotional states (depression, anxiety, and stress) during the pandemic. Participants were administered a series of questionnaires, which included the 48-item Mental Toughness Questionnaire, the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, and the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale. Conducting a study with 21 questions to examine the effects of employment transitions on mental health and well-being. Compared to pre-COVID-19 samples from prior research, participants reported increased degrees of despair, stress, and anxiety. Specifically, respondents who had lost their work during the pandemic expressed elevated levels of negative emotional states. Nevertheless, those with significant psychological resilience had lower levels of melancholy, worry, and stress. Moreover, the analysis of moderation studies showed a correlation between mindfulness training (MT) and employment status in the forecasting of depression, anxiety, and stress. The results of our study indicate that MT may have potential in mitigating the adverse psychological effects of the pandemic on people. However, more long-term research is necessary to validate these findings (Neil, 2021).

As stated by Mujtaba (2020), downsizing, or laying off workers refers to the deliberate reduction of a substantial number of persons or workforce with the aim of enhancing organizational performance and economic prospects. Downsizing offers many immediate advantages, such as enhanced profitability, bankruptcy prevention, establishment of new connections, restructuring, and removal of unproductive or disengaged employees. Employees may feel a range of contradictory emotions, such as dismay, stress, regret, or envy, in response to layoffs or downsizing in a corporation. Moreover, layoffs have the potential to diminish the pleasure and loyalty of existing workers towards the company, resulting in decreased performance. Human resource professionals and managers must effectively manage the psychological impact of layoffs. The initial financial challenges resulting from a layoff may have detrimental effects on both the physical and psychological well-being of a worker, perhaps leading to bankruptcy, depression, and more severe health issues. Due to the possibility of unemployment lasting for a duration of six months or more, layoffs might result in significant long-term effects. Unemployed individuals who are unable to find new employment may suffer emotions of despair and a decline in self-assurance. The paper provides a comprehensive analysis of workforce reductions and their impact on workers. Moreover, this research highlights the role of HR specialists in layoffs, which is to ensure that the company can enhance its overall efficiency. Human resources experts have the responsibility to ensure that the process of laying off employees is carried out in a manner that is legal, ethical, and socially acceptable. They also play a crucial role in managing the transition of people and the impact on the overall corporate culture. Managers have the ability to use new technology or robots in order to reduce the need for a large workforce in the future. Additionally, they may contemplate relocating the company or organization to a place that is in close proximity to the necessary resources.

The COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting economic recession have had an adverse effect on the emotional well-being of several individuals and have posed extra challenges for those who already struggle with mental illness and substance abuse problems. During the pandemic, over 40% of individuals in the United States have had symptoms of anxiety or depressive illness. This percentage has been relatively stable and is much higher than the 10% of those who had similar symptoms from January to June 2019. Based on the July 2020 KFF Health Tracking Poll, a significant number of individuals are experiencing adverse effects on their mental health and overall well-being due to the coronavirus. These effects include challenges with sleep and appetite, heightened alcohol use or drug abuse, and deterioration of pre-existing chronic diseases. As the pandemic advances, ongoing and necessary public health measures subject an increasing number of persons to circumstances linked to adverse mental health consequences, such as isolation and unemployment (Panchal, 2021).

Economic impact of COVID-19

This article aims to quantify the decline in financial well-being caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, using Klein's findings as a basis. The existing theoretical framework emphasizes the impact of financial risk perception and financial anxiety on financial well-being. The objective of this investigation is to ascertain if public workers, because to the influence on their job stability, are less susceptible to the pandemic compared to private employees. A study was done on 1222 individuals, using structural equation modeling and multi-group invariance testing. The results indicate that those with lower financial well-being are primarily influenced by feelings of financial concern and exposure to potential risks. Public officials have comparatively lesser declines in financial well-being, concerns, and risks as compared to other professions. During a pandemic, when the risk of unemployment and income reduction is increased, job stability serves as a kind of insurance, offering public workers more financial security and minimizing the impact on their financial well-being. There is evidence to indicate that it will be challenging to reduce the financial consequences of the pandemic in countries where a significant proportion of workers are engaged in temporary or informal jobs. Interventions aimed at alleviating anxiety, together with government policies focused on redistributing income and lowering unemployment, serve as effective measures for mitigating the negative impact on one's financial well-being.

Fornaro (2020) states that the Covid-19 coronavirus is rapidly spreading over the globe. The current COVID-19 pandemic is expected to have significant economic consequences in addition to its effects on public health. The virus is anticipated to cause a detrimental supply shock to the global economy by compelling companies to shut down and disrupting global supply chains (OECD, 2020). In this concise statement, the researchers assessed the possibility, which they think is pessimistic, of a substantial and enduring supply disruption caused by COVID-19. The researchers could not find any evidence to support the notion that this scenario was more probable than the ones that were more optimistic. There is a possibility that the virus might lead to a mild and short-lived global recession, which would then be followed by a rapid recovery in the form of a V (Wren-Lewis, 2020). Due to the significant uncertainty surrounding the

future evolution of the pandemic, it is essential to analyze the macroeconomic implications of more pessimistic scenarios. The researchers use a straightforward analytic approach to accomplish this task. Furthermore, three outcomes were emphasized. Initially, the proliferation of the virus might potentially decrease global demand. Implementing monetary stimulus measures would be advantageous in this situation to mitigate the adverse effects of the coronavirus on employment and productivity. Furthermore, there is a possibility of a supply-demand doom cycle occurring, which would worsen the supply disruption caused by the virus. Furthermore, this sickness has the potential to subject the global economy to stagnation traps, characterized by prolonged periods of sluggish growth and elevated unemployment rates resulting from pessimistic market sentiments. In this case, it will be necessary to implement assertive fiscal policy measures to revive the global economy from its downturn. Prior to commencing, it is necessary to provide a disclaimer. Both the model and the conclusions that follow are mostly derived from previously published literature.

Kuchler (2019) found that people rely on recent personal experiences to make forecasts about collective economic outcomes based on new survey data. The variations in home prices that have been recently seen in the local area have an impact on how respondents perceive future changes in house prices. Furthermore, when there is a higher level of volatility in house prices, respondents tend to provide a wider range of projections for future house price movements. Upon examining the variability in work status across individuals, the researchers found that those who have directly experienced unemployment tend to hold a more negative outlook on future nationwide unemployment. Extrapolation is not connected to the instructiveness of personal experiences, goes against risk adjustment, and is more noticeable in those with less sophistication.

The pandemic's effect on education

Aladsani (2021) states that COVID-19 has significantly affected the everyday educational routines of students, teachers, administrators, and parents. Parents residing in low-income and disadvantaged communities are disproportionately impacted by the epidemic in terms of their children's distant learning. The research examined the perspectives, predictions, and suggestions of low-income families' female breadwinner parents on their children's distant learning. Information was collected from a sample of 12 mothers who participated in a three-phase focus group study. The data obtained from the focus group discussions were categorized thematically into three distinct groups: (1) financial problems, (2) social and cultural issues, and (3) educational matters. Moreover, the data revealed the main factors influencing the breadwinners' future expectations for enhancing education, including both general and technology considerations. This applies to scenarios where schools return to in-person teaching or adopt a blended learning approach. For the next academic year, the providers of financial support suggested three approaches to education. The study's results can inform the creation of educational policies and training programs that offer crucial social and technological assistance to low-income families. This will help address their needs in the online learning environment and improve digital equality for low-income families who are at a higher risk of educational disadvantages.

Methodology

Research Design

The Phenomenological Research Design was employed in this study (Smith & Osborn, 2007). It aimed to characterize primary breadwinners' experiences, such as their experience of abruptly losing their work during the epidemic. Internal psychological processes such as their personal experiences and connections with others were also considered.

For the research, Phenomenological Research Design was employed, which focused on experiences, events, and occurrences. This study used an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) (Smith & Osborn, 2007) methodology in exploratory data collection. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, as defined by Osborn (2007), is a qualitative technique that strives to give extensive investigations of personal lived experiences. The goal of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis is to investigate in depth how participants make meaning of their personal and social worlds; consequently, the major emphasis of an IPA research is the participants' perception of specific experiences and events (Smith, 2007). Furthermore, IPA seeks to identify what life experiences mean to individuals via an in-depth reflective inquiry approach. IPA employs phenomenological thinking to return "to the things themselves" (Peat et.al, 2018).

The phenomenological study design was used to explain the structure, meaning, and substance of a person's lived experiences centered on a certain occurrence (Simon, 2011). Furthermore, according to Groenewald (2004), phenomenological research design is a study that aims to comprehend people's views, viewpoints, and knowledge of a certain occurrence.

Being qualitative research that relies mostly on interviewing and seeing respondents to gain access to their perspectives on what constitutes validity (FitzPatrick, 2018), the researcher gathered information using semi-structured and in-depth interviews, namely one-on-one teleconference interviews. Creswell (2009) defined qualitative research as a process in which the study would rely solely on "text and picture data" that has distinct rates of data analysis and focuses on a diverse range of techniques to inquiry. The application of qualitative analysis allows for a more methodical and scientific study of the meanings of social phenomena as experienced by individuals (Dante, 2015).

Participants

This study was conducted with ten (10) breadwinners who lost their jobs and are currently living in NCR. This study employed a purposive sampling technique. The participants underwent a validation as part of the selection of respondents for the study, participants that met the study criteria proceeded to the interview process. Seven (7) criteria had to be firmly met: (1) Breadwinners, people who brought in the main source of income of the family lost their jobs due to redundancy or downsizing, (2) can either be male or female (3) ages from 20 years old to 45 years old, (4) must be married (5) must have at least have 5 years and above work experience in any field such as corporate and field work, (7) can either be a high school or college graduate. In selecting the participants, the researcher considered only those who can respond to the interview. Also, the participants were asked to answer a qualifier question then a list of semi-structured questions.

According to Etikan (2016), the purposive sampling approach, also known as judgment sampling, is the careful selection of a participant based on the attributes the person possesses. Purposive sampling was employed in this type of qualitative study (Engle et al., 1998). In this study, the researcher used his or her own discretion in selecting a co-researcher to engage in the study.

This research included only breadwinners who had lost their employment. Furthermore, just ten (10) people took part in the study. As for the criterion for selecting target participants, they must be willing to engage as co-researchers and be able to answer and reply to interviews. It centered on knowing what it's like from the participants' perspectives. The commitment of IPA to a full interpretive analysis of the instances is one of its distinguishing features.

Table 1. *Summary Matrix of Participants' Profile*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>No. of dependents</i>	<i>Educational attainment</i>	<i>Previous occupation</i>	<i>Employment Status</i>	<i>No. of Minor dependents</i>	<i>Spouse' occupation during COVID-19</i>
Mrs. Hardworking	38 years old	2 (Husband and child)	Tertiary Education	IT Personnel	Regular	1 child	Owens a small repair shop (Closed down during pandemic)
Mrs. Parental	40 years old	4 (Husband and 3 children)	Tertiary Education	Small Business owner	Regular	1 child	None (Stroke victim)
Mr. Supportive	44 years old	5 (Wife and 4 children)	Tertiary Education	Seafarer	Contractual	1 child	None (Housewife)
Mrs. Street Smart	42 years old	4 (Husband and 3 children)	Vocational Certificate	Hair stylist	Regular	2 children	Freelance worker (construction)
Mrs. Altruistic	32 years old	4 (Husband, 2 children and 1 parent)	Secondary Education	Admin Staff	Regular	2 children	Street vendor (Stopped due to pandemic)
Mrs. Batang Ina	27 years old	2 (Husband and child)	Secondary Education	Cashier	Regular	1 child	Helper (Stopped due to pandemic)
Mrs. Optimistic	27 years old	2 (Husband and child)	Vocational Certificate	Masseuse	Regular	1 child	Tricycle driver (Stopped due to pandemic)
Mr. Try Again	32 years old	2 (Wife and child)	Secondary Education	Janitor	Contractual	1 child	None (Housewife)
Mr. Smiling Personality	35 years old	4 (Wife and 3 children)	Tertiary Education	Seafarer	Contractual	3 children	None (Housewife)
Mr. Big Brother	28 years old	4 (Wife, child, 1 sibling and 1 parent)	Secondary Education	Welder	Contractual	1 child and 1 sister	None (Housewife)

The data in the table show the demographic profile of the co-researchers. It can be deduced from the data that the participants in this study passed the inclusion criteria specified by the researcher. Common inclusion criteria include demographic, clinical, and geographical characteristics (Patino & Ferreira, 2018). Because the co-researchers' true identities had to be kept confidential, only code names were used for this study.

Instruments

The researchers verified the questionnaire used in this study by consulting three specialists in the field of Psychology at the graduate school. This was done to ensure the validity and reliability of each question.

Informed consent. This was provided by the researcher to determine that the participant was willing to be engaged in the study and that the participant has the right to withdraw anytime. The researcher was able to follow the data privacy before, during and even after the study.

Qualifier. This was a question that identified that the participant had met all the seven (7) criteria.

Semi-structured interview. This instrument was used to gather the needed information from the participants. The researcher believes that the semi-structured interview based on the aim of the study was able to extract the important information needed to understand the experiences of the participants. This is a researcher-constructed questionnaire that underwent proper content validation procedure by a registered psychologist of the Cavite Center of Mental Health. The semi-structured interview helped to produce unflinching and meaningful outcomes of data.

Information sheet. This was used to obtain more detailed information of the profile of the participants. It contained the needed information to determine if the participants passed the criteria set for selection of sample in this study. The participants' identities were, however, kept confidential.

Field-Note. This was used in the study for note taking purposes during the interview sessions and in recording the observations concerning the study.

Recorder. This was used for audio-recording purposes in the gathering of data.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure followed this particular course:

Looking for potential participants. The researcher sought the help of colleagues and used social media platforms such as Facebook Group page and Twitter to be able to connect with potential participants.

Assessment of participants. The potential ones underwent validation through the criteria set in the selection of respondents for the study; they were asked to answer a qualifier to validate if they fit the criteria of the study. Finally, the participants, 10 breadwinners who are aged 20-45 years, were purposively sampled.

Introduction of study to participants. Then the researcher formally asked for the approval of the target participants. The researcher presented and properly explained the objective of the study.

Present Informed consent. The selected participants were asked to sign the Informed Consent letter and were told about the ethical conduct of the study. This consisted of informing them that they could withdraw participation at any times they felt the need, that their identities would be kept confidential, and that the information they would provide shall be used solely for research purposes.

Scheduling the interview sessions. The researcher scheduled interview sessions with the participants. Due to the strict protocol required during the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviews were held via googlemeet at the convenience and availability of the co-researchers.

Conducting the interview sessions. The native vocabulary was employed for easier communication and understanding between the researcher and the participants. Interview sessions lasted for 40 minutes to an hour and a half per participant. The researcher asked one question at a time to allow the co-researcher as much time as possible to reply with detailed information. Furthermore, the researcher was able to conduct three interview sessions with each participant to collect data for the study. Every interview was conducted online via google meet without major distractions or other kinds of disruptions. A follow up interview was scheduled after finishing the first session for additional in-depth interview with the co-researcher. The interview centered on the experiences of breadwinners who lost their job during the pandemic. Following each interview session, the researcher was able to assure notifying the co-researcher about the following meeting in order to have an appropriate closure.

Confirmation of responses/Member data check. The data that were gathered were firstly consulted with the participants to check for validation and confirmation of their experiences and responses to the interview.

Debriefing was conducted to ensure that the participants understood what went on and why the study was conducted.

Data Analysis

Following the interview process, through notetaking, audio-recordings, and observation of non-verbal cues during the interview, necessary data were documented and collated for the phase of data analysis. Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) according to (Smith & Osborn, 2007) was used in analyzing the gathered data.

Reading and Rereading. Reading and rereading were done as much as feasible to provide the researcher with rich evidence from participant narratives. The researcher assessed and reviewed the data gathered from the participants through reading and re-reading.

Initial Noting. The researcher took notes on the most relevant elements in the data. At this point, the researcher was permitted to provide remarks, and additional assertions were also taken note of.

Developing Emergent Themes. The researcher looked for possibly growing themes from the tales. The researcher offered a short explanation to describe the themes that emerged from the notes. The brief description allowed readers to understand how the researcher built the concepts.

Searching for Connections across Themes. The researcher selected and clustered topics. To prevent repetition, related themes were

integrated, and themes with similar patterns were placed in a separate column.

Moving to the Next Case. The researcher repeated the process with the following participant's story. The method was repeated until the final participant was reached. It benefited the researcher in gaining a thorough comprehension of each participant's narrative.

Looking for Patterns across Cases. The researcher then merged each growing topic from all of the participants' accounts. In table style, a summary of primary themes and subthemes, as well as key replies, was created. This aided the researcher in organizing the primary themes and subthemes and formalizing the findings.

Participant Checking – Participant checking allows participants to check (verify) certain areas of the interpretation of the data they submitted (Carlson, 2010). The collected data was returned to the participants for validation and confirmation based on their experiences and replies to the interview. This aided the researcher in determining whether the data analysis was consistent with the participants' experiences and instilling faith in the study.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study the researcher considered the following ethical factors:

Vulnerability of the participants. When selecting participants, the researcher ensured that the subjects could decide whether to engage in the study or not. The researcher described the study's scope. Caution was prioritized in gaining informed consent and in gathering information throughout the investigation.

Risks, benefits and safety. A rigorous assessment of predicted risk and burden drove the investigation. The researcher took precautions to ensure that the study had no detrimental influence on the participants' well-being. Debriefing was completed at the end of the interview so that participants were fully informed about the study and allowed to ask clarifying questions.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The researcher recognized the need of transparency. The researcher did not provide any information about the volunteers that may expose them to injury or social shame. Furthermore, the researcher stressed the participant's ability to remove data or information and to refuse to answer any question. The participant's right to privacy was honored.

Withdrawal of participation. The researcher provided the participants the option to withdraw from the study at any moment and without explanation. Participants had the right to leave if they felt uncomfortable at any point of the conduct of the study..

Token for participants. At the end of the study, the researcher gave each participant a memento of appreciation for their assistance. The token presented to the participants was not large, but it was adequate to show thanks.

Results and Discussion

This section answers the three research questions presented in the introduction. It explored the experiences of the participants who are breadwinners of their families and who lost their jobs during the pandemic. The validity of each theme was discussed and confirmed by the advisor who specializes in clinical psychology.

What are the lived experiences of breadwinners who had lost their jobs during the pandemic?

Based on the narratives obtained from the responses of the co-researchers, most of the breadwinners interviewed were minimum wage earners, while some earned more, but they all had one thing in common. Because of the COVID-19 crisis, they were all laid off or had their contracts not extended. The narratives also revealed that the breadwinners were unprepared for their financial duties (example: school fees, necessities, health, and house bills). The co-researchers said that their dismissal was so abrupt that they didn't have time to hunt for another employment.

Because of the family's inability to contribute financially, tension ensued, resulting in fights and disagreements among family members. However, it was also claimed, as per the co-researchers' narratives, that despite tensions amongst the members, their friendship became stronger because of the scenario. It brought them closer together since they now see one another frequently and can learn new things about their family; it also improves their faith and allows them to work together to overcome this difficult circumstance. The pandemic provided an opportunity for them to focus and be innovative and resourceful in overcoming and resolving challenges as a family, rather than having simply one person shoulder all the duties.

What themes emerged from the lived experiences of breadwinners who lost their jobs during the pandemic?

The results are presented first in a tabulated form, then followed by a discussion of the analysis and the interpretation. Two major themes emerged from the narratives, each with subthemes. These are:

1. Positive Realizations with subthemes: (1) Stronger bond with family members; (2) Deeper faith in higher power; (3) Family members helping each other
2. Negative outcomes with subthemes: (1) Pessimism of breadwinners; (2) Loss of confidence; (3) Disillusionment; (4) Distance between husband and wife.

Table 2. Theme 1. Positive Realizations

Sub-Themes	Sub Theme Defining Elements	Key Responses	Code
1.1 Stronger bond with family members	As the sense of strengthening the relationship of the family.	<p><i>"Naisip ko yung sinabi ng asawa ko na, kakayanin naming kahit anong mangyari."</i> (I thought of what my husband said to me, that we will get through this)</p>	Mrs. Batang Ina
		<p><i>"Ang pamilya ko kasi sila ang priority ko at mahal na mahal ko sila. Lahat gagawin ko para sa kanila."</i> (My family is my priority. I love them and I'll do anything for them.)</p>	Mr. Smiling Personality
		<p><i>"Sila ang support system ko lagi nila akong pinapayuhan na mababayaran namin lahat ng utang at makakaahon din kami, na babalik din ulit to sa dati."</i> (They are my support system; they always assure me that everything will be okay, and everything will be back to normal)</p>	Mrs. Parental
		<p><i>"I am really thankful for the support of my family and friends for giving me mental support to lessen this depression I am having right now."</i> (I am thankful for the support of my family and friends for giving me mental support to lessen this depression I am having right now.)</p>	Mrs. Hardworking
		<p><i>"Una palang, sakanila na ako kumukuha ng lakas ng loob."</i> (I get my strength from them)</p>	Mr. Big brother
1.2 Deeper faith in Higher power	As the sense of strengthening faith in Higher power	<p><i>"Yung ngayon palang na na kahit papano may mga taong tumutulong samin"</i> (Even at the beginning, some were already helping up)</p>	Mrs. Optimistic
		<p><i>"Na may awa po ang diyos. Na matatapos din po. Lalo na po ngayon na nag aano na sila ng mga bakuna. Sana po sa susunod na taon okay na ang lahat. At balik na po sa dati. Tiwala lang. Yan po ang lagging sinasabi ng asawa ko sakin."</i> (God will not let us down, Especailly right now that there is already a vaccine. I hope that it will continue and all of us be back to normal)</p>	Mr. Try Again
		<p><i>"May liwanag ang buhay at sa tingin ko hindi ako papabayaan ng dyos pagsubok lamang ito"</i> (When there's life, there's light. And I don't think that God would let me down)</p>	Mr. Smiling Personality
		<p><i>"Hope. Ganon. Iniisip ko na lang nab aka hindi ko pa kasi time magkawork or baka meron nakaalan sakin. Na challenges from above para mabuksan yung pag iisip ko ganon."</i> (Hope. I think that maybe theres a reason why I still don't have work, maybe there will be challenges from above. That's what I was thinking</p>	Mrs. Hardworking
		<p><i>"Ang diyos unang una. Naniniwala ako na hindi naman ito ibibigay kung hindi naming kaya eh"</i> (Firstly, God. I believe that wont give me anything that I cant handle.)</p>	Mrs. Optimistic
		<p><i>"Lilipas din daw. Tsaka pag dasasal para gabayan kami ng panginoon at hindi pabayaan"</i> (This too shall pass. [we] just pray that God will guide us)</p>	Mrs. Batang Ina
		<p><i>"Diyos. Alam ko naman at ramdam ko naman na di nya ako, kami pababayaan eh."</i> (God. I know and feel that he will always guide me.)</p>	Mrs. Altruistic
<p><i>"Basta po wag lang bibitaw siguro kahit mahirap at samahan ng dasal."</i> (You just have to hold on along with prayers)</p>	Mr. Big Brother		

1.3 Family members helping each other	As the sense of initiative of members to find ways to contribute	“ <i>Buti na nga lang nakapasa sa scholarship ni (politician) yung anak ko, kaya nakapag enroll sa college.</i> ” (It was a good thing that my son got a scholarship for college)	Mrs. Street Smart
		“ <i>Bali dyan kami nag invests nung nag start yung pandemic, tatal dami nag papa deliver ngayon so naisip ni misis na business.</i> ” (That’s were we invested during this pandemic. Since many were into deliveries, so my wife thought of that business)	Mr. Smiling Personality
		“ <i>Di ko alam na magaling [Resourceful] pala yung asawa ko. Kaya sila sila po ang nag bibigay buhay sa kin.</i> ” (I didn’t know that my wife was resourceful. That’s why they’re my life)	Mr. Supportive
		“ <i>Narealized ko po ma’am na sila [relatives] nga tinutulungan kami.</i> ” (I realized that my relatives were helping us.)	Mrs. Hardworking
	As a sense of comfort	“ <i>Tapos tuwing nakikita ko sila, ayon naiisip ko nalang din na may pag asa pa naman. Matatapos din naman tong pandemic. Maaayos din buhay naming</i> ” (Eveytime, I see them, I see that we do have a chance to make this work. That we’ll get through this)	Mr. Big Brother
		“ <i>Nakaya nga daw naming na umalis at sumugal dito sa maynila nung mga bata pa lang kami. Ngayon pa ba daw na may anak at mas matanda na kami</i> ” (I overcome that day when we were kids and went to gamble in manila. Its too late to let go now, my husband said)	Mrs. Batang Ina

Table 2 shows the theme Positive Realizations with subthemes: (1) Stronger bond with family members; (2) Deeper faith in higher power; (3) Family members helping each other.

While it is true that the negative effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was felt by the co-participants, based on the narratives that were gathered, it is shown that it also has a positive impact in terms of self and relationship with the family. According to Ming-Te Wang's (2021) research, parental work-from-home (WFH) status predicted an increase in parental warmth, which predicted an increase in child positive affect and a decrease in child negative affect. Due to the situation with the pandemic, some works were required to have a work from home setting which meant having time to spent with the family, seeing as the situation is based on parents being able to spend quality time with their families means strengthening their bond and deepening their affection towards each other.

An article released by World Vision on June 2020 states that some of the positive effects of the COVID-19 pandemic to a family is life skills for improved resilience of a child, enhancement of critical thinking in terms of ways on how to be resourceful and be creative, having a deeper faith towards higher power and quality for the whole family.

Sub-theme 1.1 Stronger bond with family members as experienced by the co-researchers based on their narratives, Parental WFH status indicated an increase in parental warmth, which predicted an increase in child positive affects according to Ming-Te Wang (2021). Seeing as the situation of the pandemic brought home parents who were working mostly onsite pre-pandemic, now the parents were given a chance to spend quality time with their families as well as creating new bonds and discovering skills of the members that weren't known before.

Furthermore, being the pandemic had provided families to spend time together also brought new understanding to them that made them closer. The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mrs. Parental: “*Sila ang support system ko lagi nila akong pinapayuhan na mababayaran namin lahat ng utang at makakaahon din kami, na babalik din ulit to sa dati.*”

(*They are my support system; they always assure me that everything will be okay, and everything will be back to normal*)

Mrs. Optimistic: “*Yung ngayon palang na na kahit papano may mga taong tumutulong samin*”

(*Even at the beginning, some were already helping up*)

Mr. Smiling Personality: “*Ang pamilya ko kasi sila ang priority ko at mahal na mahal ko sila. Lahat gagawin ko para sa kanila.*”

(*My family is my priority. I love them and I’ll do anything for them.*)

Reports from the co-researchers show how thankful and appreciative they are towards people who help them get through this pandemic and that it strengthens their bond as a family unit. With reference to the study of Valdez (2022), it is viewed that experiencing gratitude is healthy for the well-being and has favorable psychological effect on a person. Hence, the co-researchers, expressed the importance of a stable and strong support system which can include family, friends or colleagues and although monetary material is important, the realization of looking past superficial factors and instead focusing on health, safety and family relationship is what makes a healthy life.

Sub-theme 1.2 Deeper faith in Higher Power as defined by the co-researchers, is the spirituality that binds the mind and soul of a person. Based on the narratives given by the co-researchers having faith in higher power brings hope to people because of the trust that this Higher Power will provide. It brings assurance to people that everything will be fine, one just has to believe, and by believing, people will perceive more on the positive side of the situation. This is supported by TrongLuu (2022) who states that positive adaptations or changes such as a deeper appreciation for life, planning of new life routes, improvement of personal strengths, building social relationships and an open spiritually will be beneficial to an individual dealing with unpleasant eventualities.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mr. Try Again: *“Na may awa po ang diyos. Na matatapos din po. Lalo na po ngayon na nag aano na sila ng mga bakuna. Sana po sa sususnod na taon okay na ang lahat. At balik na po sa dati. Tiwala lang. Yan po ang lagging sinasabi ng asawa ko sakin.”*

(God will not let us down, Especially right now that there is already a vaccine. I hope that it will continue and all of us be back to normal)

Mr. Smiling Personality: *“May liwanag ang buhay at sa tingin ko hindi ako papabayaang ng dyos pagsubok lamang ito”*

(When there's life, there's light. And I don't think that God would let me down)

Mrs. Optimistic: *“Ang diyos unang una. Naniniwala ako na hindi naman ito ibibigay kung hindi naming kaya eh”*

(Firstly, God. I believe that He won't give me anything that I can't handle.”

Mrs. Altruistic: *“Diyos. Alam ko naman at ramdam ko naman na di nya ako, kami pabayaang eh.”*

(God. I know and feel that he will always guide me.)

The stories of the co-researchers show that they view spirituality as an aid in mental relaxation, allowing the mind to be less tense when dealing with crisis. Their belief in a higher power that provides gives them peace and hope.

Sub-theme 1.3 Family members helping each other as referenced by the views of the co-researchers is shown in each one's initiative to help contribute productively within the family. Hence, motivation impacts the daily life of individuals, enables them to be ready and to modify the habits. Based on the study of Rathore (2015), it is stated that motivation is as much influenced by extrinsic elements as it is also influenced by intrinsic elements such as life satisfaction, life orientation and a sense of hope to a person.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mrs. Street Smart: *“Buti na nga lang nakapasa sa scholarship ni (politician) yung anak ko, kaya nakapag enroll sa college.”*

(It was a good thing that my son got a scholarship for college)

MR. SMILING PERSONALITY: *“Bali dyan kami nag invests nung nag start yung pandemic, tatal dami nag papa deliver ngayon so naisip ni misis na business.”*

(That's were we invested during this pandemic. Since many were into deliveries, so my wife thought of that business)

Mr. Supportive: *“Di ko alam na magaling [Resourceful] pala yung asawa ko. Kaya sila sila po ang nag bibigay buhay sakin.”*

(I didn't know that my wife was resourceful. That's why they're my life)

Mrs. Hardworking: *“Narealized ko po ma'am na sila [relatives] nga tinutulungan kami.”*

(I realized that my relatives were helping us.)

Summarizing the findings from each of the co-researchers' narratives, one can see initiative among the members in providing aid and help to the family. Rathore (2015) states that motivation is as much influenced by extrinsic elements as it is also influenced by intrinsic elements such as life satisfaction, life orientation and a sense of hope to a person. Relating it to the findings from the narratives, helping the family to be productive allows moving forward and is based not only on how strong and stable the family relationship is but also on how strong the mental and emotional aspect of the person.

Mrs. Batang Ina: *“Nakaya nga daw naming na umalis at sumugal dito sa maynila nung mga bata pa lang kami. Ngayon pa ba daw na may anak at mas matanda na kami”*

(I overcome that day when we were kids and went to gamble in manila. Its too late to let go now, my husband said)

On the other hand, one co-researcher states that she found help and consolation from her husband who became her support and strength in terms of striving to be productive.

Table 3. *Theme 2. Negative Outcomes*

Sub-Themes	Sub Theme Defining Elements	Key Responses	Code
2.1 Pessimism of breadwinners	Choose negative thinking;	<i>“Pero sa tulad ko parang parating nasa baba lang. Pinag iigihan mo naman pero parang wala ding nangyayari. Kaya mahirap po talaga. Mahirap.”</i> (It’s difficult for someone like me. I mean, you’re doing your best but still nothing happens. That’s why it’s hard.	Mr. Try Again
	A sense of overthinking negatively;	<i>“Kaya mahirap din minsan kung iisipin kung ano ng aba saysay ng buhay ko”</i> (That’s why it is hard, and you’ll sometimes think that there is no purpose in life)	Mrs. Street Smart
	Feeling helpless;	<i>“Kaso ang hirap din, dami din nag bibusiness ng ganon ngayon,”</i> (Its still difficult. A lot are opening their business now a days)	Mr. Smiling Personality
	Cannot enjoy external factors of life	<i>“It actually adds up to my mind na baka worthless talaga ako dahil nothing good is really happening to me.”</i> (It adds up to my mind na baka worthless talaga ako dahil nothing good is really happening to me.)	Mrs. Hardworking
		<i>“Wala naman akong magawa,”</i> (I can’t even do anything)	Mr. Smiling Personality
		<i>“Oo pero, hindi ko sya gusto isama sa pag hihirap ko”</i> (Yes but, I don’t want to bring him [down] with me)	Mrs. Parental
		<i>“Nung time na yon, na nawalan nako ng work talagang wala nakong naisip kundi paano na? paano na ako? paano na kami. ako lang ang pinaka inaasahan ng pamilya ko.”</i> (That time, I lost my job, and I couldn’t stop thinking about what now? What am I gonna do? Us? Im the only one who can provide for them)	Mr. Big Brother
2.2 Loss of confidence	Questioning oneself;	<i>“Maraming pumapasok sa aking isipan na puro “bakit ganito bakit ganyan ang nangyayari” dumarating sa punto na ako’y nahihirapan na gusto ko na lang sumuko, nakakapagod.”</i> (A lot of things were roaming through my mind like, why is this happening, it got to a point where I didn’t know what to do and just wanted to give up because I was tired)	Mrs. Optimistic
	A sense of inferiority;	<i>“But now? Where can I go? Paano mag relax? Paano ako makakapag provide sa family ko?”</i> (But now? Where can I go? How can I relax? How can I provide for my family?)	Mrs. Hardworking
	A sense of shame;	<i>“Some of my colleagues naman they have a job eh, sabay sabay kami nawalan ng work? Bakit sila nakuha na? Pero ba’t ako hindi pa din?”</i> (Some of my colleagues already found jobs, the fact that we all got laid off at the same time. So why don’t I still get one [job]?)	Mrs. Hardworking
	<i>“Totoo pala yon na makakaramdam ka na parang wala nang kwenta buhay mo. Halos oras oras ko kasi iniisip non yung mga problema, mga pagkukulang ko.”</i> (Its true that you feel as if your life is useless. Cause everything you think about are problems. All my short comings)	Mr. Big Brother	

		<p>“Minsan nga lang parang nakakapanliit kasi parang wala akong silbi sa bahay. Ako lang ba yung walang ginagawa.” (Sometimes I feel so little cause I can’t provide for my family. I am the only one who isn’t productive)</p>	Mr. Supportive
		<p>“Pero iba din minsan kapag alam mo yung ikaw yung inaasahan.” (Its different when you know that youre the one the one whom they are counting on)</p>	Mrs. Optimistic
		<p>“Paano ako haharap sa kanila. Na anong klaseng ama ako na uuwi dun na wala man lang akong dala” (How can I even face the? What kind of father I am to come home to them and have nothing?)</p>	Mr. Try Again
2.3 Disillusionment	False hopes; Losing hope; A sense of unexpected situation	<p>“Tawagan na lang daw kami [company]. Pero wala naman na tumawag. Isip ko na na matagal tagal naman yung lingkod ko sakanila. Sana kahit ako nalang, alam naman nila yung situation ko.” (They said that they’ll just call us [company]. But they didn’t. I thought they ive served them well enough to consider me back, knowing that I are aware of my situation)</p>	Mrs. Batang Ina
		<p>“Dapat sasampa na ako nung April 2020 pero na delay na nadelay kasi walang sagot pa daw yung principal.” (I was supposed to embark last April 2020, but there still wasn’t any response fro the principal)</p>	Mr. Supportive
		<p>“Yes, I sent a lot of work applications, pero hanggang ngayon walang tumatangap saakin.” (Yes, I sent a lot of work applications but still not even one called)</p>	Mrs. Hardworking
		<p>“Naisip ko noon na di naman yun makakaapekto, pero nung biglang nababalita na yung sa mga ibang bansa dumadami na mga cases at nag papanic na mga tao, kinabahan na kami ng misis ko.” (I thought then that I weren’t be affected. But when the news about the cases were rapidly increasing and that people were starting to panic. Me and my wife got worried)</p>	Mr. Smiling Personality
		<p>“Kaya hindi ko alam ang gagawin ko. Sunod sunod. Hirap na nga mag hanap ng trabaho nagkaganto pa. Mabuti sana kung mag isa lang ako. O kung wala akong anak. Kaso may responsibilidad kaming mag asawa” (That’s why I didn’t know what to do. One after the other. Its already difficult to find a job then this, it’ll be a lot diffrent if I just had myself and didn’t have any responsibilities.</p>	Mrs. Optimistic
2.4 Distance between husband and wife.	Frequent arguments; Choice to isolate; A sense of misunderstanding; Financial stress	<p>“gabi gabi na lang kami ng aaway ni misis” (Every night my wife and I argue)</p>	Mr. Try Again
		<p>“Wala kaming ginawa kundi mag away.” (We didn’t do anything aside from fighting)</p>	Mrs. Street Smart
		<p>“Nahiya ako, as in. I spent a lot of time sa room ko, to the point na ka pag kakain na they knock my door to remind me na it’s lunchtime or dinnertime na.”” (I was ashamed. I didn’t leave my room to the point that I didn’t eat even if they called me and reminded me about the time)</p>	Mrs. Hardworking
		<p>“Tas pag uwi ko ayun. Galit na galit sila saakin.” (Then when I got home, they were so mad at me)</p>	Mr. Supportive
		<p>“Tulad nung nasabi ko nakakapagod. Madalas kami mag away sa pera.” (Like I’ve said, I’m tired. We argue all the time)</p>	Mrs. Altruistic

<p>“<i>Napadalas pag aaway naming mag asawa. Lalo na kung usapang pera, gastusin. Pareho kaming nawalan ng trabaho eh.</i>” (We [husband] frequently fight. Especially if it comes to money since both of got don't have a job)</p>	Mrs. Batang Ina
<p>“<i>Nagkakainitan kami ng ulo madalas ni nung asawa ko. Napadalas yung pag aaway naming. Lalo na sa pinansyal na bagay. Pang kain, pang renta, yung para pa sa anak ko.</i>” (We [wife] often get in each other's nerves. We argue a lot especially when it came to financial things like rent, food and for our child.)</p>	Mrs. Optimistic

Table 3 shows the Negative outcomes with subthemes: (1) Pessimism of breadwinners; (2) lost of confidence; (3) Disillusionment; (4) Distance between husband and wife.

The COVID-19 pandemic, according to Bittmann (2021), has a detrimental impact on people's subjective well-being. The findings from the narratives of the co-researchers show the negative outcomes caused by the loss of job of the breadwinners due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Apart from problems with physical and mental health and the large-scale economic struggles brought about by the pandemic, it is evident that the loss of employment among the breadwinners in the study has brought negative impacts also on the relationships inside the household. According to Ming-Te Wang's (2021) research, when a parent's employment is lost, there is an increase in parent-child conflict, which predicts a decrease in child positive affect and an increase in child negative affect. In this study, the relationships most affected are the relationships with oneself and with the spouse.

The narratives below show the co-researchers' experiences from losing their job during the pandemic and how these affected their mental state and perception as well as their marital relationships.

Sub-theme 2.1 Pessimism of breadwinners as referenced by the views of the co-researchers has indeed become a prevailing feeling. The study from Benigno (2018) stated that pessimistic expectations can lead to very persistent, or even permanent, slumps characterized by high unemployment and weak individual growth. However, a pessimistic mindset is not particularly hopeful, it demonstrates little optimism, and can be depressing for some people who are experiencing different eventualities. It implies that people feel evil outweighs good and that negative things are more likely to occur when being faced with difficult challenges such as unemployment and loss of financial income.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mr. Try Again: “*Pero sa tulad ko parang parating nasa baba lang. Pinag iigihan mo naman pero parang wala ding nangyayari. Kaya mahirap po talaga. Mahirap.*”

(It difficult for someone like me. I mean, youre doing your best but still nothing happens. That's why its hard.

Mrs. Street Smart: “*Kaya mahirap din minsan kung iisipin kung ano ng aba saysay ng buhay ko*”

(That's why it is hard and you'll sometimes think that there is no purpose in life)

Responses from some of the co-researchers state their pessimistic perception brought by the pandemic; the co-researchers experience lack of hope. Hopelessness is not only experienced during the time of the pandemic but also when individuals can no longer avoid negative situations as per Seligman (1967) on his theory of Learned Helplessness.

Mr. Smiling Personality: “*Wala naman akong magawa,*”

(I can't even do anything)

Mrs. Parental: “*Oo pero, hindi ko sya gusto isama sa pag hihirap ko*”

(Yes but, I don't want to bring him [down] with me)

Mr. Big Brother: “*Nung time na yon, na nawalan nako ng work talagang wala nakong naisip kundi paano na? paano na ako? paano na kami. ako lang ang pinaka inaasahan ng pamilya ko.*”

(That time, I lost my job, and I couldn't stop thinking about what now? What am I gonna do? Us? Im the only one who can provide for them)

However, some of the co-researchers shared their sentiments about their experience about the pain and struggles caused by eventualities brought by the pandemic and is unable to overcome it. People with pessimistic perceptions are more stressed and have fewer coping abilities, pessimism among older individuals is also associated with higher stress levels, a larger focus on the less positive aspects of their lives, and a greater inclination to look back on life with more negativity in general, lowering life satisfaction. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) define psychological stress as "a specific interaction between the individual and the environment that the person perceives as

straining or surpassing his or her resources and harming his or her well-being."

Sub-theme 2.2 Loss of confidence is expressed by the co-researchers as a sense of inferiority of a person experiencing emotional and mental distress due to a crisis. In reference to the literature of Hiswáls (2017), people consider their jobs as the foundation of their sense of belonging, and changes in their financial situation impact their social lives; also, the sense of losing confidence and hopelessness, all of which had an influence on their physical well-being.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mrs. Hardworking: *"Some of my colleagues naman they have a job eh, sabay sabay kami nawalan ng work? Bakit sila nakuha na? Pero ba't ako hindi pa din?"*

(Some of my colleagues already found jobs, the fact that we all got laid off at the same time. So why don't I still get one [job]?)

Mr. Supportive: *"Minsan nga lang parang nakakapanliit kasi parang wala akong silbi sa bahay. Ako lang ba yung walang ginagawa."*

(Sometimes I feel so little cause I can't provide for my family. I am the only one who isn't productive.)

The influence of unemployment on mental health likely appears in various ways including a reduction of self-worth. Below are the views of some co-researchers regarding their experience when they felt emotional distress caused by a misunderstanding and the feeling of inferiority.

Mrs. Optimistic: *"Pero iba din minsan kapag alam mo yung ikaw yung inaasahan."*

(Its different when you know that youre the one the one whom they are counting on)

Mr. Try Again: *"Paano ako haharap sa kanila. Na anong klaseng ama ako na uuwi dun na wala man lang akong dala"*

(How can I even face the? What kind of father I am to come home to them and have nothing?)

Referring to the study of Keddis (2018) stating the role of parents as the sole provider of needs of the family, it is said that the longer an individual is unable to provide for the family the more the person questions his self-worth.

Sub-theme 2.3 Disillusionment During the COVID-19 experience, wide disillusionment, tiredness, and exhaustion, as well as the hatred and division associated with issues of financial and personal problems, contributed to the deterioration of the early-phase community camaraderie; the camaraderie was replaced by disagreement and hostility (Perry M. Gee, Marla J. Weston, & Tom Harshman, 2022). Based on the reported response of the co-researchers are disappointments of the outcomes of the situation that one does not have control over.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mrs. Batang Ina: *"Tawagan na lang daw kami [company]. Pero wala naman na tumawag. Isip ko na na matagal tagal naman yung lingkod ko sakanila. Sana kahit ako nalang, alam naman nila yung situation ko."*

(They said that they'll just call us [company]. But they didn't. I thought they've served them well enough to consider me back, knowing that I am aware of my situation).

Mr. Supportive: *"Dapat sasampa na ako nung April 2020 pero na delay na nadelay kasi walang sagot pa daw yung principal."*

(I was supposed to embark last April 2020, but there still wasn't any response from the principal)

Mr. Smiling Personality: *"Naisip ko noon na di naman yun makakaapekto, pero nung biglang nababalita na yung sa mga ibang bansa dumadami na mga cases at nag papanic na mga tao, kinabahan na kami ng misis ko."*

(I thought then that I wouldn't be affected. But when the news about the cases were rapidly increasing and that people were starting to panic, me and my wife got worried)

Mrs. Optimistic: *"Kaya hindi ko alam ang gagawin ko. Sunod sunod. Hirap na nga mag hanap ng trabaho nagkaganto pa. Mabuti sana kung mag isa lang ako. O kung wala akong anak. Kaso may responsibilidad kaming mag asawa"*

(That's why I didn't know what to do. One after the other. It's already difficult to find a job then this, it'll be a lot different if I just had myself and didn't have any responsibilities).

As seen in the narratives of the co-researchers, there was a sense of disappointment over an uncontrolled situation which was the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the study of Perry M. Gee, Marla J. Weston, & Tom Harshman (2022) people reflect, the truth of the situation and their power to make a difference become obvious. The first period of hope is followed by a period of disappointment. As the demands of reacting increase, layers of effect become obvious, and resource constraints become apparent, discouragement, tiredness, and exhaustion set in.

Sub-theme 2.4 Distance between husband-and-wife indicates that the co-researchers experience impaired expression of love, affection,

respect, and communication among family members during the pandemic. The study of Bosch (2019) emphasizes that family relationships are critical in a sense that a person's reaction to job issues have been observed to be influenced by family stress since the family domain is one of the most significant areas outside of work and during the pandemic family relationships tend to escalate and deplete because of the crisis. The lack of communication and understanding may lead to relationship conflicts among family members.

The following are some of the responses from the narratives of the co-researchers:

Mr. Try Again: *"gabi gabi na lang kami ng aaway ni misis"*

(Every night my wife and I argue)

Mrs. Street Smart: *"Wala kaming ginawa kundi mag away."*

(We didn't do anything aside from fighting)

Mr. Supportive: *"Tas pag uwi ko ayun. Galit na galit sila sakin."*

(Then when I got home, they were so mad at me)

Mrs. Hardworking: *"Nahiya ako, as in. I spent a lot of time sa room ko, to the point na ka pag kakain na they have to knock my door to remind me na it's lunchtime or dinnertime na."*

(I was ashamed. I didn't leave my room to the point that I didn't eat even if they called me and reminded me about the time)

Mrs. Batang Ina: *"Napadalas pag aaway naming mag asawa. Lalo na kung usapang pera, gastusin. Pareho kaming nawalan ng trabaho eh."*

(We [husband] frequently fight. Especially if it comes to money since both of got don't have a job)

Mrs. Optimistic: *"Nagkakainitan kami ng ulo madalas nung asawa ko. Napadalas yung pag aaway naming. Lalo na sa pinansyal na bagay. Pang kain, pang renta, yung para pa sa anak ko."*

(We [wife] often get in each other's nerves. We argue a lot especially when it came to financial things like rent, food and for our child.)

The narratives of the co-researchers show that stressful situations include a tear in the quality and stability of the emotional and physical relationship of spouses brought by the pandemic situation. Supporting the findings is the study of Overall (2022) stating that stressful situations might compromise not only the quality and stability of a couple's relationship but also the family function.

What insights can be gleaned from the experiences of the breadwinners who lost their jobs?

Based on the narratives that were obtained from the co-researchers, the researcher was able to extract certain common issues that breadwinners faced during this pandemic:

Family Relationships. Conflicts were raised due to the situation of the pandemic, such as misunderstandings, miscommunication that led to distance within the family, stated by Bosch (2019), family relationships are critical in the sense that a person's reaction to job issues has been observed to be influenced by family stress because the family domain is one of the most significant areas outside of work and during the pandemic family relationships tend to escalate and deplete due to the pandemic crisis. However, based on the latter part, there was a positive realization in terms of providing support and comfort for each member of the family, and discover skills of family members. According to Ming-Te Wang's (2021) parents were given the opportunity to spend quality time with their family while also forming new ties and learning previously unknown skills of their children.

Coping with the pandemic. As stated from the narratives of the co-researchers, the increase of family bonding and comfort, a lot were able to spend time with their family members and discover skills of one another that helped them build a stronger bond with each other. Also, there was an increase of trust in Higher power when faced in difficult situations as supported by the study of TrongLuu (2022) who stated that believing or having faith in higher power brings hope and assurance to people that everything will be fine and by believing it directs people to focus on the positive side rather than dwelling on the negative situation.

Financial Problems. Given the sudden economic impact caused by the loss of their jobs due to COVID-19 pandemic, the co-researchers encountered grave financial problems. The co-researchers weren't prepared, and their savings, if there were at all, were not enough to sustain the ongoing daily needs of the families making these supposed breadwinners feel largely accountable for the ensuing difficulties.

Stress towards job loss. Due to the sudden impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, the co-researchers suffered from stress and pressure brought by the pandemic situation. Co-researchers experience loss of confidence towards self, and some distanced themselves from the members of the family due to miscommunication and misunderstandings. This confirms what Bosch (2019) found in his study that relationships with the family are crucial in terms of reactions towards job loss and stress since family is the significant area outside of work itself.

Here are the key findings of the research. The primary catalyst for the resurgence of breadwinners is a positive realization. Gaining

awareness of the favorable consequences in a given scenario may be beneficial for an individual enduring a challenging circumstance, as it can assist them in surmounting more obstacles and positively impact their future job performance. Enhanced familial connection. The co-researchers' narratives revealed that spending more time with family members resulted in a better bond. The bond between breadwinners and their family was shown to be reinforced by affection and comfort. The combination of comfort and the recognition of what is essential had a beneficial impact on the bad circumstance. Enhanced belief in a Supreme Being. The testimonies of the co-researchers revealed an increased conviction and confidence in a higher power throughout the COVID-19 epidemic. The results also demonstrate the beneficial impact of religion on individuals, enabling them to direct their attention towards the good aspects of a given scenario. Relatives' Mutual assistance. The results indicate that under challenging circumstances, family members provide mutual assistance to make meaningful contributions to the family unit. According to the accounts of the co-researchers, the family members devised strategies to financially assist the home. These included establishing a small company, seeking scholarships, and enhancing the overall support network.

Another prominent issue that arises from their experiences is the adverse consequences that the pandemic crisis has had onto the primary earner and their families. Lack of trust. The co-researchers have seen a decline in confidence resulting from a sense of inferiority owing to the rapid loss of employment during the epidemic, as well as the inability to support their families as they did before the outbreak. Additionally, this also includes the phenomenon of being unable to get employment despite submitting several job applications. Disillusionment. According to the accounts of the co-researchers, the unexpected onset of the pandemic resulted in both economic and psychological distress, leading to a sense of disillusionment with the situation. The co-researchers attempted to navigate the circumstance but encountered unfavorable outcomes such as being unsuccessful in job applications or receiving unexpected results despite their expectations. Spousal distance. The study not only assessed the co-researchers' financial capacities and psychological states, but also evaluated the bond between couples. According to the accounts provided by the co-researchers, they often engaged in conflicts with their wives because of the pandemic circumstances. The factors contributing to the distance include financial constraints, associated stress, misunderstandings, disappointments, and a lack of communication among both spouses and family members.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are reached:

The pandemic afforded families more time together and this helped the breadwinners to spend some quality time to enjoy getting to know more about each member of the family and discover skills that helped the family to manage and cope with the pandemic. Based on the findings, overall, it made the family closer to each other rather than finding their relationships deteriorate due to conflicts and difficulties. It made the family more open to one another and focus on the positive outcomes of a negative situation. The families became more productive in terms of strengthening the support system and to have initiative to contribute for the family. It has also shown the deepening of faith in a higher power when faced with difficult situations, faith becoming the essential fuel to be more positive and believe that they will overcome this pandemic as a family.

The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated the pessimistic mindset of the breadwinners, and the effect of unemployment was quite detrimental, causing the co-researchers to become unprepared with their finances due to the sudden unemployment. That pushed the co-researchers to disillusionment; experiencing disappointment while in the midst of the pandemic had led to the loss of confidence of the breadwinners due to the inability to provide like they used to during the pre-pandemic but also the job rejections that were faced as well as feeling of inferiority when seeing the members of the family being productive. Furthermore, a distance was created between spouses due to the negative thoughts about oneself and miscommunications and misunderstandings that led to frequent fights and arguments.

In the light of the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher recommends that psychologists and other helping professionals be tapped to help the people who have borne the brunt of the pandemic, particularly those breadwinners who have lost their jobs and are encountering not only problems of providing for their families' needs but also problems affecting their well-being. It is recommended that they offer assistance to these breadwinners and their families in the form of counseling interventions that can lead eventually to self-help programs that aim at the establishment of the following as goals:

Strong Family Bond, consisting of maintaining or strengthening the relationship of the family despite having to experience challenging eventualities and overcome them together as one family. The following are also suggested to support family relationships:

Quality time, spending productive time with the members of the family, knowing the members more, communicating to avoid distance between members and looking for activities that members can do together.

Support system, establishing initiative towards contribution within the family, enhancement of growth of each member to be able to provide the needed support of one another most especially during the time of the pandemic.

Self Enhancement, improving one's skills to avoid negative and destructive thoughts about themselves and any situation, to be constructive in facing difficult eventualities so as to overcome them. The following are also advised to help enhance the self of the breadwinner:

Stress management, since the issue of the pandemic is still not resolved, and may still bring stress to the breadwinners; establishing effective breathing exercises as practice in managing stress.

Coping mechanisms, establishing effective and productive way of coping with stress and pressure in times of difficulty to manage one's emotions and behavior well.

Communication, being one of the factors that can lead to distance between family members, thus, the need to establish open and good communication within the family, to be able to fully understand each other and know all the differences that need to be addressed most especially during the time of the pandemic.

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